

SHORT NOTES

Metallic Complexes of Schiff's Base Derived from *o*-Hydroxyacetophenone and Ethylenediamine

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Pfeiffer and co-workers¹ studied the preparation, properties, and constitution of a large number of metal-chelate complexes of oxalydimines and oxyketimines with spiral-like or polycyclic rings. In these, various *o*-oxyaldehydes and diketones were allowed to condense with monamines, diamines, and even amides and esters of amino-acids in presence of metallic salts. Similar studies of metallic complexes of Schiff's bases derived from sulphosalicylaldehyde, resoreylaldehyde, and β -hydroxynaphthaldehyde with amines, amides, amino-acids, and aminohydroxamic acids were made by Ráy and Mukherjee². Ráy and Poddar³ used 3-aldehydo-salicylic acid as the aldehyde component of the Schiff bases and described the preparation, properties, and structures of some metallic complexes formed with the resultant bases.

The present work deals with the preparation and properties of Schiff's base from *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and ethylenediamine and its complex salts with metals like copper, nickel, manganese, cobalt, vanadium, and uranium.

Schiff's base of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with ethylenediamine was prepared by refluxing *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (2 moles) and ethylenediamine (one mole) in ethanolic medium for about half an hour on a water bath. The substance forms shining yellow crystals (m. p. 188-89°), insoluble in water but soluble in hot ethanol. These are decomposed by strong acids and alkalis on warming.

The metallic complexes of the Schiff base were prepared by refluxing one mole of the base and one mole of the corresponding metal acetate (chloride in the case of the vanadyl salt) for 2 hours on a water bath. On cooling, shining crystalline products were obtained. These are soluble in ethanol but insoluble in water. The compounds were decomposed by strong mineral acids and alkalis on warming. Analysis of the products revealed the formation of complexes of the general formula $[M(SB)]$, where $M = Cu^{+2}, Ni^{+2}, Co^{+2}, Mn^{+2}, UO_2^{+2}$, and VO^{+2} and SBH_2 is a molecule of the Schiff base derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and ethylenediamine. Structurally, the complexes may be represented as

1. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1937, 149, 217; 1939, 151, 145; 1940, 155, 77; 1942, 159, 313; *Ber.*, 1944, 77A, 59.
2. *This Journal*, 1950, 27, 707; 1955, 32, 505, 567, 581, 604, 633.
3. *Proc. Symposium on the Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds*, Agra, 1959.

With ferric ions, the base produced in acid medium a strong violet colour which changed to red when the pH of the solution was increased; but no solid compound could be isolated in the pure state from the solutions.

The results of the measurements of magnetic susceptibility values of the compounds are shown below. The magnetic moment values of the complexes are more or less similar to those of the corresponding metallic ions and hence they seem to suggest the formation of outer-orbital or associated type of complexes.

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	Colour.	Temp.	Effective μ_n .
1	Copper- <i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone-ethylenediamine	Violet	21.5°	1.83
2	Nickel- <i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone. "	Golden yellow	"	3.55
3	Cobalt- <i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone. "	Red	"	4.49
4	Manganese- <i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone. "	Deep green	21.7°	6.85
5	Uranyl- <i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone. "	Orange-red	"	Diamagnetic
6	Vanadyl- <i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone. "	Bluish green	21.7°	2.50

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